

Estimating the Transitional Dynamics of Money Demand in Ghana

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Abstract

The theoretical fundamentals of money demand functions extrapolate how economic agents may choose to demand and hold money rather than other liquid assets. The selection of choices however, depends on the underlining structure and stability of the monetary mechanism of a given economy. The raison d'être of the research was to investigate the transitional dynamics of money demand in the Ghanaian economy. The scale variables used in the estimations are real money balances and real GDP while the opportunity cost variables include exchange rate and inflation rate. The empirical results from the long run Johansen cointegration causality revealed the existence of "at least" three cointegration vectors. A comparative analysis of OLS and ARDL was estimated and the residuals extracted for the short run ECM estimations. The coefficients of real GDP, exchange rate and inflation from the long and short run examination were robust and significant at different magnitudes. The CUSUM, CUSUMQ and Chow test of stability showed money demand to be somewhat stable in the Ghanaian economy from 1983 to 2013. The study strongly recommended that narrow money should be used as monetary aggregates targeting in the Ghanaian economy.

Keywords; Money demand, monetary aggregates, opportunity cost, cointegration, Chow test, Ghana.

JEL: E41, Demand for Money, E52, Monetary policy, C22, Time-Series Models.

1.0 Introduction

Both microeconomic and macroeconomic factors in Ghana's financial sector have changed significantly over the past few years. This has forced the Ghanaian monetary authorities (Bank of Ghana) to be smart and allow prices and other indicators to determine the allocation of resources by the market forces of demand and supply. The household continued to dominate the demand for money in the economy with only a handful of electronic investment instruments existing in the formal banking sectors.

The banking industry in Ghana has been undergoing a revolutionary process since 2016. This is attributed to the Bank of Ghana (BoG) recent policy of stabilizing the economy and pathing way for financial engineering to be realized. In Ghana, the financial sector influenced the money market partially. Nevertheless, financial deepening is spreading quickly across the country, this is done in the form of executing and making available small loans to borrowers who has prospects of repaying, mobilizing groups and engaging them in "SUSU" derivatives, new developments in payment instruments such as debit and credit cards have aided in the reduction of the demand for cash in daily transactions. All these have aided in achieving financial inclusiveness.

Money market instruments are employed by the Bank of Ghana to command liquidity in the financial system holistically while ensuring stability in the banking system. Volatility in the money market has often been caused by several factors which include excess money in circulation, uncontrolled deposits interest rates, inflations and somewhat exchange rates. It's therefore imperative to consider this dynamism in estimating the demand for money in every economy especially a developing one like Ghana.

Inflation targeting is one of the centermost underpinnings of most developing economies. The central bank of Ghana adopted this principle in 2007 where inflation was hedged at 5%, however, there were short run shocks associated with its implementations. Nevertheless, inflation targeting is a flexible concept but not rigid. This footstep taken by BoG saw inflation dropped to substantial digits (10.7% in 2010 and 9.2% in 2012). Inflation growth in Ghana has been quite repulsive since 1999-2018, for instance, Consumer prices in Ghana advanced to 10.4% year-on-year in March of 2018, enabling from a 10.6% upsurge in the preceding month, largely due to a strike in clothing, footwear and transport prices.

According to Goldberg and Knetter (1997) exchange rate pass-through is the percentage change in local currency import prices resulting from a one percent change in the exchange rate between the exporting and importing countries. Exchange rate pass-through therefore is the effect (positive or negative) of exchange rates on import and export prices, consumer prices or inflation, investments as well as trade volumes. Engel and Rogers (1996) established that adventure through the US-Canada rim can significantly increase comparative price instability and that exchange rate instabilities explicate about one-third of the volatility increase. In this case, US-Canada rim is a significant factor of comparative price volatilities even after making due allowance for the role of distance. Parsley and Wei (2001) confirmed previous findings that crossing national borders enhances meaningfully to price dispersion.

The growth rates of the monetary aggregates are mainly due to the higher rates of GDP within that period. For instance, average GDP growth rate between 2000 and 2012 was over 6% as compared to lower rate of about 3.14% between 1985 and 1999.

Monetary growth also possesses deviance and self-correcting effects on every economy. Bawumia et al. (2003) postulates that a tightening of monetary policy through an increase in the monetary authority's official rates (or other rates that the Central Banks may see appropriate for monetary purposes) will lead to a fall in the demand for money, prices and output while the exchange rate will rise. What this means for the Ghanaian economy is that, following a contractionary monetary policy shock, interest rates rise the demand for money and output falls. In the short run, inflation rises and the real effect of interest rate hike is felt in the economy.

The demand for and supply of money are key determinants in explaining the spending patterns of consumers and investors in every agrarian and industrialized economy. The demand for money is mostly influence by consumers motives and expenditure patterns. According to John Maynard Keynes (1930 & 1936), three reasons or motives influenced people to demand for money, namely; Transactionary, precautionary and speculative motives. These motives were stipulated in his book "General Theory of Employment, Interest and Money (1936)". He offered a vivid explanation of how interest rate is determined by money demand and supply, he agued that the demand for money as an asset depends on the interest foregone by not holding bonds, he described "bonds" to represent stocks and other less liquid assets in general, as well as government bonds. Interest rates, he claims, cannot be a reward for saving as such because, if a person stores his savings in cash, keeping it under his mattress say, he will receive no interest. He noted that, the transactional motive of demand for money is realized when economic agents prefer liquidity for current expenditure, and this mostly is a function of income such that the higher the income the more preferences for liquidity. The precautionary demand for money is influenced by unforeseen or unexpected social circumstances; precautionary demand is also affected by income. Speculative motives are related to interest rate, when interest rates are low money demand increases and vice visa hence, people retained liquidity for the purpose of bond prices volatility and interest unpredictability. Keynes money demand function is formulated as; real money demand is a function of income and interest rate

$$RMd = U(Y, i)$$

(1)

Other economists who agree with the assertion of Keynes analysis on the role of income in money demand include Adekunle (1968) and Sowa (1993). Similar to those economists is Baumol (1952) and Tobin (1956), who introduced interest rate as one of the explanatory variables in the transactions demand for money. This theory of interest rate and inflation postulate that nominal interest rates would increase less than one-to-one with respect to expected inflation. This is because in response to inflation the public would demand and hold less money balances and more in other assets, which would drive interest rates down. In other words, an increase in the exogenous demand and growth rate of money increases the nominal interest rate and velocity of money but decreases the real interest rate. Interest rate measures the opportunity cost of holding money (Gujarati, 1968; Adenkule, 1968). Intuitively, if interest rates rise the opportunity cost of holding money increases therefore money demand falls.

The demand for money at a specified period can be affected by the process of financial engineering, innovation and deregulation. These affects both the interest elasticity of different monetary aggregates and the balances held at each level of the transfiguration of monetary policy and interest rates. Another source of instability may be swings in the precautionary demand for money, related to changes in economic shocks, and institutional dynamism. Moreover, having a stable money demand is very important, the existence of a well- specified and stable relationship between money and other macroeconomic variables, like price, and exchange rate can be perceived as a prerequisite for the use of monetary aggregates in the conduct of monetary policy.

In estimating the demand for money in any economy, the scale variable and the opportunity cost variables are fundamentally of high consideration. There is however, a monetary dialogue as to which variable really constituent a scale and an opportunity cost variable in developing economics like Ghana; it is inflation? one-month interest rate? Or annual average interest rate? Most studies employed different variables in trying to estimate a stable money demand function.

Notwithstanding the above, a handful of research has been conducted in trying to note the non-observability of money demand in different spheres with different methodologically typologies, these approaches seems to have digressions in terms of the results and variables employed. For instance, Sober Mall (2013) estimated the real money demand function in Pakistan by using variables such as real income, foreign exchange rate, call money rates and Interest rate while Dennis Nchor & Václav Adamec (2016) uses variables which includes; M1, M2, interest rate and real GDP to investigate the stability of money demand in Ghana. These and among other studies presented different descriptions of estimating the money demand. However, most of these studies used interest rate as a proxy for the opportunity cost variable, this is misleading largely because in developing economies like Ghana, inflation is quite volatile and has a direct effect on the money demand in the economy than interest rate. The uniqueness of this study is its incorporation and used of inflation as

an opportunity cost variable. This study therefore seeks to offer quite a vivid explanations and comprehension as well as to select a more suitable and appropriate variables to estimate the transitional dynamics of money demand in Ghana.

2.0 Literature Review

In trying to establish a stable money demand function, some parameters appeared to be crucial and determinant to explaining why money demand varies from developed to developing countries. Most early research on money demand outlined key demands for understanding money demand in every economy. Medieval researchers such as John Maynard Keynes (1930 & 1936), Friedman (1959), Adegunle (1968), and Subramanain S. Sriram (1999) Hendry and Erricson (1991 a, b) Johansen and Juselius (1990), distinguished key macroeconomic variables which were classified as scale and opportunity cost parameters. Contemporary researchers however, found a mixer and somewhat pervasive and perverse relationship of these variables at different domain niches.

Emmanuel Opoku (2017), investigated the determinants of money demand in Ghana with ARDL model as the baseline econometric analysis. The results evidenced the existence of long run relationship between money demand and its determinants. The empirical output further showed that expected inflation rate and exchange rate exhibits a robust short long run effects on money demand. The role of real interest rate is only recognized in the long-run whereas the impact of financial innovation resulting from the on-going financial sector reforms only affect the transitional dynamics of the money market conditions. There is also an ample evidence of instability in the money demand relationship as a result of inflation and exchange rate volatility. Moreover, given that the wealth effect phenomena hold in Ghana, the paper concludes by suggesting that policies directed towards regulating and maintaining stable exchange rates and low and steady inflation would be necessary to maintain stable money demand and thus enhance the effectiveness of monetary policy in Ghana.

Dennis Nchor & Václav Adamec (2016) investigated the stability of money demand in Ghana.

The CUSUM tests of stability of parameter showed and Chow test that, the money demand function was stable over the period and did indicate any structural breaks over the period under consideration. The output from the Johansen's cointegration (ARDL) approach revealed that, the variables were cointegrated and non-stationary, on these bases, an error correction model (ECM), was used to estimate the factors that affect real money aggregate in Ghana economy from 1990 to 2014. The study projected the results using two set of variables for real demand for money; M1 and M2+. This was done given the assumption that the demand for money was equal to the supply of money. The results showed that, interest rate affects the real money demand in the short run, while GDP affects the level of demand for money in the long run. The error correction term in each of the cases showed that, 18 % of nonconformities in the real demand for money is adjusted annually.

Simmons (1992) investigated the demand for narrow money for five African countries (Democratic Republic of the Congo, Cote d'Ivoire, Mauritius, Morocco and Tunisia) within an ECM outline. This study stresses the role of opportunity cost variables counting the domestic interest rate and expected exchange- rate depreciation. His empirical results indicated that the domestic interest rate is a significant determinant of the real demand for money functions for three out of the five countries, whereas external opportunity cost variables were substantial for only one country. He also discovered that, four out of the five countries, inflation exhibits an enormous important role in determining the demand for money.

Arize, A.C. (1989) formulated an Asian money demand functions and argued that foreign interest rates, exchange rate depreciation and technological change are the most important determinants in Pakistan, Philippines, South Korea, and Thailand.

Kannapiran C. A. (2001) uses the Error-correction model (ECM) for short-run dynamics of money demand function model to study the properties of money demand in Papua New Guinea (PNG). His empirical results suggested that an appropriate monetary policy for monetary targeting regime as anticipated by the central bank in PNG. Though, the income elasticity of money demand is relatively lower than the most of developing countries. Yet, a stable relationship between the demand for money in PNG and its determinants: Real GDP, nominal interest rate and inflation rate offered a strong support to the above stated policy implications.

Nachega, J.C. (2001) investigates the behavior of M2 broad money demand while trying to modeled a summary in an open economy in Cameroon. His findings revealed that, own rate of return is positively delicate and rate of inflation, currency substitution and foreign interest rate are negatively and undesirably sensitive to the broad money demand. These estimations signposted the attachment of unitary income elasticity with the quantity theory of money as well as the source of inflation as imported is revealed above stated process of money demand functions.

Cuthbertson, K. and D. Bredin (2001) concluded that uncertain environments of Czech Republic raised at the end of 1992 are infrequency caused of any currency substitution concerns. Nonetheless, despite the data limitation since the crumbling of the Czech-Slovak Republics at earlier of 1993.

Cuthbertson et al. (2001) found a long-run existence between real demand for money aggregates and its determinants: real income and inflation rate.

Bahmani-Oskooee and Rehman (2005) used quarterly data from 1973 to 2000 to estimate the demand for money for seven Asian countries. Using ARDL approach and CUSUM and CUSUMSQ tests, they found that in some Asian countries even though real M1 or monetary aggregates are cointegrated with their determinants, the estimated parameters are unstable.

Akinlo (2006) used quarterly data over the period 1970:1-2002:4 and the ARDL approach combined with CUSUM and CUSUMSQ tests, to examine the cointegrating property and stability of M2 money demand for Nigeria. The results show M2 to be cointegrated with income, interest rate and exchange rate. Moreover, the results revealed somewhat stable relation mainly with the CUSUM test.

Kogar (1995) tried to test whether there exists a stable long run money demand function for Turkey and Israel. For the Turkish case, it was found that there exists a long run relationship between real money (M1 and M2) demand, real income, inflation and exchange rate with an elasticity of income slightly lower than unity and also an elasticity of exchange rate significantly low.

Bawumia et al (2003) noted in their studies “An Investigation of the Transmission Mechanisms of Monetary Policy in Ghana” from 1983 to 1999 that exchange rates, money supply and real income depicts the existence of a long and short run equilibrium relationship between inflation, money supply, the exchange rate, and real income. A Structural Vector Error Correction Analysis was used in their investigations.

Similarly, Mutluer and Barlas (2002) analyzed broad money demand in Turkey between 1987 and 2001 using various structural reforms and deregulations. Their results indicated the existence of long run relationship for real broad money in Turkey, with a unitary income elasticity estimated.

Halicioglu and Ugur (2005) analyzed the stability of the narrow money demand function (M1) in Turkey for the period 1950–2002. They estimated and tested for the stability of Turkish M1 by procedure proposed by Pesaran et al, (2001) alongside CUSUM and CUSUMSQ stability tests. They demonstrated that there is a stable money demand function and it could be used as a transitional target of monetary policy in Turkey.

3.0 Methodology

Macroeconomics explained the demand for money to depend entirely on two key fundamental frameworks; scale variable and the opportunity cost of holding it. The scale variable as a determinant of money demand is often viewed to measure the amount of economic activities consumers engaged in a given economy, that is the wealth the economy generates at a given point in time. Its sometimes apparently measure the volume of economic transactions or expenditures of economic agents in both closed and opened economy. The scale variable as mentioned earlier is associated with wealth however, due to challenges in obtaining the general wealth of the economy, especially for developing once like Ghana it's imperative to use real GDP as the scale variable. Other variable often used in money demand estimating functions is the opportunity cost variable. This parameter is frequently used to measure the return of money against other financial assets such as bonds, stocks and cryptocurrencies. In financial economics, the opportunity cost variable is tagged as interest rate, however, inflation rate is typically used to proxy interest rate especially for developing economics who do not have stable measurement of interest rate.

The theoretically specification of the money demand function is stated as;

$$\frac{MD}{P} = L(Y, R) \quad (2)$$

Where MD is the demand for money, P is inflation (the price level), Y is the real income level which represents the scale variable, and R is the opportunity cost variable. The opportunity cost variable is interest rate or can be proxied us inflation. Taking the currency swap or substitution phenomenon into justification, many studies on the demand for money in developing countries often include exchange rate variable in the standard function of money demand as suggested first by Mundell (1963). Taking the currency substitution phenomena into account, the money demand function is extended further to include exchange rate as follows;

$$\frac{MD}{P} = L(Y, R, EXR) \quad (3)$$

Where EXR is interpreted as nominal exchange rates, which is defined as the amount of domestic currency per unit of foreign currency.

Taking the natural log of equation three to obtained a theoretical configuration for this study is displayed in equation four;

$$\ln\left(\frac{MD_t}{P_t}\right) = b_0 + b_1 \ln RGDP_t + b_2 INF_t + b_3 \ln EXR_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (4)$$

Where $\ln$ is natural log, ε is the error term $RGDP$ is real gross domestic product, INF is inflation rate and EXR is exchange rate.

3.1 Data Source

The study employed time series data from the websites of international monetary fund and world bank development indicators databases for 1983-2013 period. The variables extracted includes; broad money growth, measured as the annual percentage broad money growth, GDP growth measured as annual percentage growth rate of GDP at market prices based on constant local currency, GDP deflator which is measured by the annual growth rate of the GDP implicit deflator and shows the rate of price change in the economy as a whole, exchange rate (annual average based on monthly averages) is the local currency (Ghana cedis) units relative to the U.S. dollar, and finally, inflation rate.

3.2 Setting up the variables

Existing studies measured real GDP at 2005 constant prices as the scale variable (see Emmanuel Opoku, 2017, Dennis Nchor & Václav Adamec, 2016), however, in this study, real GDP as an income variable in the money demand function is measured as a ratio of GDP to GDP deflator. Real money demand balances are also derived from monetary aggregates growth (M2+). In basic economic literature, the money demand at any given time frame must be equal to its supply, therefore M1, M2 and M2+ are often proxied as a measure of money demand. The demand for real money balances in this study is measured as the ratio of M2 to GDP Deflator. Inflation and exchange rate are taken literally to represent their generality.

3.3 Analytical econometric technique

The study adopted the autoregressive distributed lag model (ARDL), Johansen's cointegration approach, ordinary least squares (OLS) and error correction model (ECM) for the empirical analysis. The attractiveness of the ARDL model is that, it pacts with a single cointegration equation as well as taking into consideration all the variables to be integrated in model are I(0) or I(1) or even both I(0) and I(1) integrated (Pesaran and Shin 1999). This model has a reparameterization approach to co-integration of non-stationary and stationary variables and can be unified for cointegration through ARDL approach and error-correction (EC) processes. Pesaran and Shin (1999) argued that ARDL approach to cointegration provides robust and "spurious free" results which are fantastic with consistent estimates of the long-run coefficients in case of small samples. The model is expressed empirically by adopting the study variables in equation (4) as;

$$\left(\frac{MD_t}{P_t}\right) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \left(\frac{MD_t}{P_t}\right)_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_z \left(\frac{MD_t}{P_t}\right)_{t-D} + \varphi_0 RGDP_t + \varphi_1 RGDP_{t-1} + \dots + \varphi_h RGDP_{t-h} + \omega_0 INF + \omega_1 INF_{t-1} + \dots + \omega_j INF_{t-r} + \gamma_0 EXR_t + \gamma_1 EXR_{t-1} + \dots + \gamma_s EXR_{t-m} + \varepsilon_t \quad (5)$$

Equation (5) is stretched by attaching elasticities to attain the ARDL model as follows;

$$\Delta \ln\left(\frac{MD_t}{P_t}\right) = a_0 + \sum_{i=1}^q a_{1i} \Delta \ln\left(\frac{MD_{t-i}}{P_{t-i}}\right) + \sum_{i=1}^q a_{2i} \Delta \ln(RGDP_{t-i}) + \sum_{i=1}^q a_{3i} \Delta \ln(INF_{t-i}) + \sum_{i=1}^q a_{4i} \Delta \ln(EXR_{t-i}) + a_5 \Delta \ln\left(\frac{MD_{t-1}}{P_{t-1}}\right) + a_6 \ln RGDP_{t-1} + a_7 INF_{t-1} + a_8 \ln EXR_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \quad (6)$$

Where q is the optimal lag length, Δ represents the first difference operator, a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4 , are the short run coefficients or dynamics of the model, while a_5, a_6, a_7, a_8 represents the long run characteristics and elasticities of the model. Before estimating equation (6), an F-statistic test is performed on the null hypothesis $H_0: a_5 = a_6 = a_7 = a_8 = 0$ for no cointegration or no long-run relationship between the variables against the alternative hypothesis $H_1: a_5 \neq a_6 \neq a_7 \neq a_8 \neq 0$ of long-run cointegration or long-run relationship between the variables. When the regressors considered are statistically significant and co-integrated, an unrestricted error correction model (ECM) is used to estimate the given long run relationships among them. The unrestricted error correction model (ECM) is given as;

$$\Delta \ln \left(\frac{Mdt}{Pt} \right) = a_0 + \sum_{i=1}^{y_1} a_{1i} \Delta \ln \left(\frac{Mdt-i}{Pt-i} \right) + \sum_{i=1}^{y_2} a_{2i} \Delta \ln(RGDP_{t-i}) + \sum_{i=1}^{y_3} a_{3i} \Delta \ln(INF_{t-i}) + \sum_{i=1}^{y_4} a_{4i} \Delta \ln(EXR_{t-i}) \gamma EC_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \quad (7)$$

Note; $\left(\frac{Mdt}{Pt} \right)$, is represented as RMD in the data presentation.

Where $y_1, y_2, y_3,$ and y_4 represents the optimal lags of the ECM model and γ depict the speed of adjustment from disequilibrium to equilibrium base on previous shocks, EC is the error term emanated from the long run analysis.

3.4 Statistical test configurations

In every time series data, variables are a concoction of stationary and non-stationary properties and may results to spurious estimates if OLS is applied for the analysis. On these bases, the study performed a unit root test to evaluate these properties. We first performed the orthodox Augmented Dickey-Fuller (1979) unit root test and supplement it with Philips–Perron (PP) unit root. Tests Person (1988). The PP test appears to provide a robust assessment, largely because, it's effective even in the existence of heteroscedastic errors and serial correlations. This test again allows for correcting unknown breaks in the configuration of the time series.

The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root test equation is stated as;

$$\Delta y_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 t + \psi y_{t-1} + a_t + \sum_{i=1}^p \Delta y_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t \quad (8)$$

Where

Y_t is the variable under consideration

t is time trend

Δ is the difference operator

ε_t is assumed to be white noise

From equation (8), the null hypothesis of stationarity is expressed as:

$H_0: \psi = 0$ (yt is non-stationary)

$H_1: \psi < 0$ (yt is stationary)

The conclusion of the test is based on the t-statistics, Once the calculated -statistic is less than the critical values provided by MacKinnon (1996), the null hypothesis is rejected or invalid and the alternative hypothesis of stationarity is accepted.

ARDL and ECM models yields a considerably consistent result when the correct lags are selected for the analysis. The study passed through lag selection process to ascertain the number of lags require for the model. According to Hundie (2014), models that have large number of lags consequently will result in residuals that appear to approach a white noise progression but may not be parsimonious nonetheless, models with shorter lag lengths are likely to be penurious but may not harvest residuals that have enough stochastic characteristics for a white noise progression. The information criteria used in this study to determine the optimum number of lags for the model included: Schwartz Information Criteria (SIC), Akaike Information Criteria (AIC), and Hannan-Quinn Criteria (HQC).

Model diagnostic test was also carried out to determine the structural breaks in the variables considered. The recursive test of CUSUM and CUSUM of squares test as well as the Chow test were performed to understand the stability of the studied variables.

4.0 Results and Discussion

4.1 Statistical Test Configurations: Testing for Stationarity and Cointegration

The study carried out the traditional Augmented Dickey-Fuller test (unit root) to test for stationarity of the variables. The Phillips-Perron test (PP) was also performed to compliment ADF test. Table 4.1 and 4.2 shows ADF and PP test respectively. From the two approaches, all the variables accept exchange rate were found to be integrated in order I(1) at both level and first difference, however, in the ADF test, exchange rate was I(0) at both level and first difference and discovered to be integrated in order I(0) and I(1) in the PP test. Since the variables were discovered to be I(1) and I(0) at level and first difference, the study proceeded to perform both ARDL bound and Johnson cointegration test so as to established a long run causality among the variables considered. The f-statistics from the ARDL bound test was (9.554277) which is greater than the upper bound critical value of 5.61 at 1% significance level, on this basis, we have satisfactory reasons to reject the null hypothesis of no long-run relationship at 1% significance level and conclude that there is long run association among the studied variables. See table 4.3 for ARDL bound test statistics.

Table 4.1 Unit Root Test (ADF) for estimating the transitional dynamics of money demand function in Ghana from 1983 to 2013.

Variables	Z(t)	ADF Test statistics	1% critical	5% critical	10% critical	MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values approx. for Z(t)	Decisions
RMD _t	Z(t)	-5.999	-3.670	-2.964	-2.621	0.0000	No Unit roots
Δ RMD _t	Z(t)	-7.297	-3.689	-2.972	-2.625	0.0000	No Unit roots
RGDP _t	Z(t)	-3.225	-3.670	-2.964	-2.621	0.02383	No Unit roots
Δ RGDP _t	Z(t)	-7.867	-3.689	-2.971	-2.625	0.0000	No Unit roots
INF _t	Z(t)	-7.651	-3.670	-2.963	-2.621	0.0000	No Unit roots
Δ INF _t	Z(t)	-4.075	-3.711	-2.981	-2.629	0.0042	No Unit roots
EXR _t	Z(t)	3.011	-3.670	-2.964	-2.621	1.0000	Unit roots
Δ EXR _t	Z(t)	2.511	-3.679	-2.968	-2.623	0.1014	Unit roots

Table 4.2 Phillips-Perron Test (PP) for estimating the transitional dynamics of money demand function in Ghana from 1983 to 2013.

Variables	Z(t)	Phillips-Perron Adj t-statistics	1% critical	5% critical	10% critical	MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values approx. for Z(t)	Decisions
RMD _t	Z(t)	-6.716	-3.670	-2.964	-2.621	0.0000	No Unit roots
Δ RMD _t	Z(t)	-13.764	-3.679	-2.968	-2.623	0.0000	No Unit roots
RGDP _t	Z(t)	-3.225	-3.670	-2.964	-2.621	0.0283	No Unit roots
Δ RGDP _t	Z(t)	-4.961	-3.679	-2.968	-2.623	0.0004	No Unit roots
INF _t	Z(t)	-7.651	-3.670	-2.963	-2.621	0.0000	No Unit roots
Δ INF _t	Z(t)	-24.8124	-3.679	-2.968	-2.623	0.0001	No Unit roots
EXR _t	Z(t)	3.011	-3.670	-2.964	-2.621	1.0000	Unit roots
Δ EXR _t	Z(t)	-3.426	-3.679	-2.968	-2.623	0.0181	No Unit roots

Note; the absolute values of Z(t) of the ADF and PP test statistics is compared with the critical values (absolute values) at 5% significance level and the null hypothesis (unit roots) is rejected if Z(t)>5% critical value.

Table 4.3 Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) Bound Test of Co-integration

Variables f(LNRMD,LNRGDP,LNEXR,INF)	F-statistic 9.554277	Cointegration Cointegration
Critical Value Bounds (significance)	Lower Bound (I0)	Upper Bound (I1)
10%	2.72	3.77
5%	3.23	4.35
2.5%	3.69	4.89
1%	4.29	5.61

4.2 Johansen's cointegration analysis for estimating the transitional dynamics of money demand function in Ghana from 1983 to 2013.

The results of the cointegration analysis is displayed in table 4.4 below. From the output, we fail to reject the hypothesis that no cointegrating vector exist in supportive of "at least three" cointegration vectors existence at 5% significance levels, from the other perspective, the existence of at most no cointegration is rejected at the same significance levels. From the above viewpoint, the normalized 1cointegrating coefficients in table 4.5 is adopted to derive the long run dynamic equation of real money demand function in Ghana in equation (9) below.

Table 4.4 Unrestricted Johansen's cointegration cointegration test (maximum Eigenvalue) for estimating the transitional dynamics of money demand function in Ghana.

Hypothesized No. of CE(S)	Max-Eigenvalue Statistic	Eigenvalue	5% Critical Value	**MacKinnon-Haugh-Michells (1999) P-Values
None*	29.383	0.637	27.584	0.0291
At Most 1*	23.289	0.552	21.131	0.0245
At Most 2*	18.225	0.466	14.265	0.0112
At Most 3*	1.762	0.059	3.841	0.1843

Note; asterisk *, donates significance levels at 5%.

Table 4.5 Normalized Cointegrating Coefficients (1cointegrating equation)

Variables	Coefficients	Standard Error
Log RMD	1.000	-
Log RGDP	.865	0.776
Log EXR	1.651	0.262
INF	-0.039	0.008
Log likelihood	-84.070	-

Long run cointegrating equation

$$\text{Log} \left(\frac{\text{MD}_t}{\text{Pt}} \right) = 0.64 + 0.87 \log(\text{RGDP}_t) - 0.04 (\text{INF}_t) + 1.65 \log(\text{EXR}_t) + \varepsilon_t \quad (9)$$

The logs attached to the variables are interpreted as elasticities. The empirical long run elasticities are compatible with the economic theoretical fundamentals behind the demand for real money balances. The estimated coefficient of real GDP which represents income elasticity in the model is approximately unitary income elastic, indicating and confirming that the long run demand for money function is unit elastic. The official real exchange rate of the Ghana cedis to the US dollar possesses a positive sign, which indicates a depreciation of the Ghanaian cedis to the US dollar. When the home currency appreciates (Ghanaian cedis) against the foreign currency (US\$) then, we expect the demand for domestic real money balances to increase. The negative sign of the semi-elastic coefficient of -0.04 inflation implies that inflation has a considerably and significantly less impact on the transitional dynamics of real money balances in Ghana for the study period considered. Please refer to appendix A for more empirical outputs on Johnson cointegration estimates.

Notwithstanding the aforementioned analysis, the study proceeded to guesstimate the short run characteristics of the model using the error correction model (ECM). Nevertheless, before estimating the ECM we deemed it conceivably vital to investigate the dynamic ordinary least squares (OLS) method and Autoregressive distributed lags (ARDL) features of real money demand (M2+). The residuals from ARDL analysis were extracted and used to estimate the short run ECM dynamics. Table 4.6 and 4.7 displays the traditional OLS and ARDL estimates respectively.

Table 4.6 Dynamic Ordinary Least Square Method, dependent variable; log RMD

Variables	Coefficients	Standard Errors	Probability Value
Log RGDP	2.367	0.762	0.004***
Log EXR	-0.726	0.242	0.006***
INF()	-0.015	0.006	0.025**
Constant	1.749	0.317	0.000***

R-square = 0.4468 Adj-R-Square=0.3854 F-Statistic = 7.2704 prob (F-Statistic) = 0.0010

Note; asterisk ***, ** donates significance levels at 1%, 5%.

Table 4.7 ARDL estimates of transitional dynamics of money demand function in Ghana.

Selected method; ARDL (2,0,2, 0)

Variables	Coefficients	Standard Errors	Probability Value
Log RMD(-1)	0.262	0.151	0.098*
Log RGDP	2.760	0.815	0.172
Log EXR(-2)	-2.926	1.678	0.096*
INF()	-0.029	0.011	0.020**
Constant	2.717	0.539	0.0001***

R-square = 0.5974 Adj-R-Square=0.4632 F-Statistic = 4.4517 prob (F-Statistic) = 0.0036

4.3 Lags selection criteria

A lag order selection criterion was carried out to determine the maximum lags for the model using various selection criterion. Based on this criteria's, one lag was recommended for the model via Akaike information criterion (AIC), Schwarz information criterion (SC) and Final prediction error (FPE). See appendix B for more details.

4.4 Short Run Error Correction Model

The residuals of the ARDL estimates were extracted, saved and employed for the short run analysis. The dynamic coefficients of ECM measure the changing characteristics of the model. The error term (ECM-1) captures the speed of adjustment to equilibrium following disequilibrium short-run shocks, caused by previous period shocks, which converges back to the long-run equilibrium. Table 4.8 presents the short run ECM estimates.

Table 4.8 Short run error correction model (ECM) estimates for estimating the transitional dynamics of money demand function in Ghana.

Variables	Coefficients	Standard Errors	Probability Value
c	0.038	0.573	0.948
$\Delta \log RMD(-1)$	2.367	0.761	0.004***
$\Delta \log RGDP(-1)$	0.951	1.237	0.017**
$\Delta \log EXR(-1)$	-0.809	0.427	0.071*
$\Delta INF(-1)$	-0.725	0.242	0.005***
ECM(-1)	-1.629	0.351	0.001***

R-square = 0.6057 Adj-R-Square=0.5199 F-Statistic = 7.0655 prob (F-Statistic) = 0.0003 Δ = first difference
 Note; asterisk ***, ** and * donates significance levels at 1%, 5% and 10% respectively.

From the above estimations, the Error Correction Model equation for the short run analysis in eq (7) is expressed as follows;

$$\text{Log} \left(\frac{MD}{P} \right)_{t-1} = 0.038 + 0.951 \log(RGDP_{t-1}) - 0.725 (INF_{t1}) - 0.809 \log(EXR_{t-1}) - 1.629 ECM_{t-1}$$

From the short run dynamics, the coefficients of all the variables considered are reliable with underling economic principles surrounding demand for real money balances. The income elasticity (RGDP) is positive and the negative signs of both exchange rate and inflation explains the decreasing impacts they have on real money balances (M2+). The negative and significant sign of the ECM-1 indicates that the cointegration causality between the encompassed variables are effective and perhaps explains the speed of adjustment to equilibrium following short-run speed of adjustment to equilibrium following short-run shocks which may be converged back to the long-run equilibrium.

4.5 Stability Diagnostic Test

In other to ensure parameter stability, the study adopted parameter diagnostic test. Money demand is a volatile economic variable and may result to structural breaks within a particular time frame. This stability check was tested using Brown et al. (1975) recommended analytical method of cumulative sum (CUSUM) and cumulative sum of squares (CUSUMQ). The Chow test was also used as compliment to the Brown et al. (1975) technique. The results from the CUSUM and CUMSUMQ in figure 4.1 depicts no structural breaks in the period investigated, this is realized because the parameters line (blue line) did not cross the 5% significance line (red line). The chow test correspondingly, revealed no structural breaks since the probability value of the f-statistics is higher than 5% significance level (see appendix C for details). The breakpoint considered was 1984, largely because in 1985, there were economic and financial sector reforms; Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) and Economic Recovery Programme (ERP) which at the time brought a somewhat financial deregulation, privatization and liberalization shocks to the Ghanaian economy. During this period, Ghana experienced in history the lowest broad money to GDP growth. In synopsis, we can say with confidence that the underling investigation parameters are stable in the long run and in the short run dynamic estimations, perhaps, real money balances (m2) exhibited a stable demand function over the entire period considered.

Figures 4.1 CUSUM Tests and CUSUM of Squares Test

5.0 Summary of Findings and Conclusion Remarks

This research empirically investigated the transitional dynamics of money demand in Ghana. The statistical test configuration resulting from ADF and PP test of stationary showed that the variables were integrated in order of I(1) and I(0), this prompted the study to carried out both bound test and Johnson cointegration of long run causality. The F-statistic (9.554277) in the bound test was higher than the upper bound critical value (5.61) and showed the existence of long run relationship. Johnson cointegration (maximum eigenvalues) establishes the existence of at least three cointegration vectors in the model. The study went further to perform a comparative analysis of the traditional OLS and ARDL pragmatic dynamics, the output from these two analyses displayed a considerably varying coefficients at different magnitudes with dissimilar robust significance levels. The short run characteristics of demand for money was estimated via the ECM technique. The stability of the model parameters was tested with CUSUM, CUSUMQ and was complimented with chow test.

The coefficients of income elasticity in both the short run and long run were approximately unitary with positive signs and significant at different levels. This confirmed the economic theoretical backing of money demand functions. The transitional impacts of inflation and exchange rate on money demand in Ghana were negative and exhibits a decreasing effect on real money balances. The stability tests portrayed that money demand in the Ghanaian economy is stable from 1983 to 2013 periods.

From the empirical analysis, its visually apparent that a stable money demand depends on exchange rate and inflations volatilities. These key economic variables have vigorous and robust impacts on the stability and transmission mechanism effect on monetary growth system in the Ghanaian economy. Bank of Ghana (BoG) should adhere and pay close monitory to curb any shocks that might come from these two variables. Again, the recent financial deregulations by BoG should be targeted to M2+ instead of M1 and M2 since M2+ is conceivably flexible to both exchange rate and inflation volatilities. BoG should also augment the deregulations reforms by setting subtle and a “double edge sword” monetary policies to control both the real and the money sectors.

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Appendix A

Johansen cointegration Analysis

Date: 02/19/19 Time: 12:38
 Sample (adjusted): 1985 2013
 Included observations: 29 after adjustments
 Trend assumption: Linear deterministic trend
 Series: LNRMD LNRGDP LNEHX INF
 Lags interval (in first differences): 1 to 1

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.636951	72.65924	47.85613	0.0001
At most 1 *	0.552042	43.27593	29.79707	0.0008
At most 2 *	0.466579	19.98729	15.49471	0.0098
At most 3	0.058963	1.762398	3.841466	0.1843

Trace test indicates 3 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Max-Eigen Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.636951	29.38331	27.58434	0.0291
At most 1 *	0.552042	23.28865	21.13162	0.0245
At most 2 *	0.466579	18.22489	14.26460	0.0112
At most 3	0.058963	1.762398	3.841466	0.1843

Max-eigenvalue test indicates 3 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Unrestricted Cointegrating Coefficients (normalized by b*S11*b=I):

LNRMD	LNRGDP	LNEHX	INF
-2.027870	7.431450	-3.347395	-0.078102
1.549455	5.142170	-0.169831	0.044706
0.835008	-6.118795	0.426227	-0.088469
0.320905	-1.768671	-2.272151	-0.017256

Unrestricted Adjustment Coefficients (alpha):

D(LNRMD)	D(LNRGDP)	D(LNEHX)	D(INF)
0.180246	-0.083817	0.023631	4.205651
-0.696352	-0.116783	0.009948	2.426908
-0.248482	0.017835	0.008169	6.965028
-0.017815	0.001763	-0.015110	0.127465

1 Cointegrating Equation(s): Log likelihood -84.07049

Normalized cointegrating coefficients (standard error in parentheses)

LNRMD	LNRGDP	LNEHX	INF
1.000000	-0.864657	1.650695	-0.038514

(0.77593) (0.26215) (0.00893)

Adjustment coefficients (standard error in parentheses)

D(LNRMD)	-0.365516 (0.43010)
D(LNRGDP)	0.169970 (0.07256)
D(LNEXH)	-0.047921 (0.02840)
D(INF)	-8.528516 (4.72748)

2 Cointegrating Equation(s): Log likelihood -72.42616

Normalized cointegrating coefficients (standard error in parentheses)

LNRMD	LNRGDP	LNEXH	INF
1.000000	0.000000	0.726941 (0.22732)	0.033444 (0.00768)
0.000000	1.000000	-0.252071 (0.06372)	-0.001384 (0.00215)

Adjustment coefficients (standard error in parentheses)

D(LNRMD)	-1.444483 (0.39454)	-2.241270 (1.39711)
D(LNRGDP)	-0.010980 (0.06690)	-1.223401 (0.23690)
D(LNEXH)	-0.032507 (0.03535)	0.226768 (0.12519)
D(INF)	-4.768132 (5.80767)	43.73366 (20.5653)

3 Cointegrating Equation(s): Log likelihood -63.31372

Normalized cointegrating coefficients (standard error in parentheses)

LNRMD	LNRGDP	LNEXH	INF
1.000000	0.000000	0.000000	-0.019231 (0.01059)
0.000000	1.000000	0.000000	0.016882 (0.00284)
0.000000	0.000000	1.000000	0.072461 (0.01202)

Adjustment coefficients (standard error in parentheses)

D(LNRMD)	-1.651967 (0.39112)	-0.720862 (1.58965)	-0.591003 (0.49213)
D(LNRGDP)	0.003913 (0.06968)	-1.332531 (0.28320)	0.308004 (0.08767)
D(LNEXH)	-0.025686 (0.03692)	0.176785 (0.15004)	-0.077310 (0.04645)
D(INF)	1.047722 (4.70445)	1.116078 (19.1206)	-11.52146 (5.91944)

Appendix B**Model selection criteria**

VAR Lag Order Selection Criteria

Endogenous variables: RMD RGDP EXH INF

Exogenous variables: C

Date: 02/19/19 Time: 15:51

Sample: 1983 2013

Included observations: 26

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-134.7075	NA	0.505832	10.66981	10.86336	10.72554
1	-73.44615	98.96062*	0.015860*	7.188165	8.155932*	7.466847
2	-58.83126	19.11178	0.019497	7.294712	9.036692	7.796339
3	-36.80562	22.02564	0.016150	6.831202	9.347395	7.555774
4	-13.60542	16.06168	0.017439	6.277340	9.567746	7.224858
5	18.12495	12.20399	0.022757	5.067312*	9.131931	6.237775*

* indicates lag order selected by the criterion

LR: sequential modified LR test statistic (each test at 5% level)

FPE: Final prediction error

AIC: Akaike information criterion

SC: Schwarz information criterion

HQ: Hannan-Quinn information criterion

Appendix C**Chow test**

Chow Breakpoint Test: 1984

Null Hypothesis: No breaks at specified breakpoints

Varying regressors: All equation variables

Equation Sample: 1983 2013

F-statistic	0.265131	Prob. F(5,21)	0.9271
Log likelihood ratio	1.897634	Prob. Chi-Square(5)	0.8631
Wald Statistic	1.325654	Prob. Chi-Square(5)	0.9323